

TEXNOLOGIK TA'LIMDA XALQARO BAHOLASH TIZIMINI JORIY ETISH METODIKASI

Baxtiyorova Sobiraxon Ixtiyor qizi

Buxoro davlat pedagogika instituti "Texnologik ta'lim"
kafedrası o'qituvchisi

Ganjayeva Ziyoda Omonboy qizi

BuxDPI "Texnologik ta'lim" yo'nalishi talabasi.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ta'lim tizimi natijasida olib borilayotgan islohotlar natijasida xalqaro baholash tizimiga oid qonun va qarorlar, xalqaro baholash dasturlari pisa, timss, EGE, Tals kabi xalqaro baholash tizimlarining qisqacha tahlili vazifalari topshiriq turlari va baholash tizimlaridan foydalanishning imkoniyatlari haqida so'z boradi.

Tayanch so'z: baholash, ta'lim tizimi, PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, kategoriya.

МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ОЦЕНИВАНИЯ В ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

Бахтиёрова Сабирахан

Преподаватель кафедры «Технологическое образование»
Бухарского государственного педагогического института.

Гянджаева Зиёда

Студентка отделения «Технологическое образование» БуксДПИ.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В результате проведенных в результате реформ системы образования, законы и решения о системе международного оценивания, программы международного оценивания, краткий анализ международных систем оценивания, таких как пиза, тимсс, ЕГЭ, Талс, задания, виды задачи и возможности использования систем оценивания.

Ключевые слова: *оценивание, система образования, PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, категория.*

METHODOLOGY OF IMPLEMENTING THE INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT SYSTEM IN TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

Bakhtiyorova Sabirakhan

Teacher of the "Technological education"
department of the Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

Ganjayeva Ziyoda

Student of BuxDPI "Technological Education" department

ABSTRACT

As a result of the reforms carried out as a result of the education system, laws and decisions on the international assessment system, international assessment programs, a brief analysis of international assessment systems such as Pisa, Timss, EGE, Tals, tasks, types of assignments and the possibilities of using assessment systems are discussed.

Key words: *assessment, educational system, PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, category.*

As a result of the reforms implemented in our country in recent years, huge economic growth indicators are being achieved, increasing the demand for qualified

personnel and mature specialists in all fields. Control of the quality of education under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers "On measures to organize international studies in the field of education quality assessment in the public education system" dated December 8, 2018 No. 997 As a result of the establishment of the National Center for the Evaluation of the Quality of Education under the State Inspectorate, it led to fundamental changes in the education system. will make a great contribution to raising the education system in my country to higher levels and improving the quality of education.

PISA (The Program for International Student Assessment) is an international program for assessing student achievement in the field of education, the main goal of the program is to evaluate the reading literacy, mathematical literacy and natural sciences of 15-year-old students. consists in evaluating literacy levels in the form of various tests. These projects aim to evaluate the creative and critical thinking of students, their ability to apply the knowledge they have acquired in life, and encourage them to develop these skills later. This program was introduced in 1997 and is held every three years, for the first time in 2000. The PISA program is a program that serves as a basis for motivating, persuading, and strengthening the knowledge of students in their preparation for life. One subject is preferred every three years, and almost 50% of the total test set belongs to this subject. PISA tests use four different test methods:

1. One-answer tests;
2. Multiple answer tests;
3. Short or detailed answer questions.
4. The student's opinion on the solution of a problem (usually in such questions, the examiner has general answers, the student's answer is not required to exactly match the answer of the test maker, the student's creativity is supported

Figure 1. Assessment of knowledge in areas in the PISA program.

What are the interactive tasks of PISA: in 2012, the participants of the first public tests were offered to include special types of tasks, that is, interactive tasks. Interactive - requires the student to conduct an independent study of a new difficult system without prior knowledge of its characteristics, through direct practical cooperation with the system, it reveals (imaginary) hypotheses, tries to test them experimentally, tries to verify the object, and is classified according to the following categories :

- competence
- natural-scientific type of knowledge
- context
- cognitive level, and in this case, pisa serves to assess the level of knowledge 15 year-old students.

Figure 2. The essence of the PISA international assessment system.

The results of the research conducted in our country will serve to improve the results of international research, target training of teachers and effective development of teaching methods in the educational process, and to improve the quality of professional education in the country.

The fact that the president and the government set specific tasks for the education system, which is not just to monitor the state of education, but also to provide information about the state of the education system, help to improve the quality of education and make it more competitive. we can be sure that it has been made clear to everyone that this is the direction to take.

In short, this PISA international assessment program will undoubtedly serve to further increase the intellectual potential of our country's youth.

REFERENCES

1. S.I. Baxtiyorova, X.Y. Hamroyeva. “Methods of Teaching Materials Science on the Basis of Innovative Educational Technologies”. Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices. Peer Reviewed International Journal.2022.Amerika.133-136pg
<https://zienjournals.com/index.php/jpip/article/view/1309>

2. S.I. Baxtiyorova. “Использование программного обеспечения в преподавании материаловедения”. “Наука, техника и образование” научно–методический журнал № 2(77) / 2021 г. Россия, Москва 80-83 с.
<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ispolzovanie-programmnogo-obespecheniya-v-prepodavanii-materialovedeniya>

3. Kakhhorov S.K., Zhuraev A.R. Method of application of virtual stands in teaching subjects of electrical engineering, radio engineering and electronics // LXII International correspondence scientific and practical conference (Boston. USA. September 22-23). 2019. – P. 44-47.

4. Jo‘rayev A.R. [Выбор оптимизированного содержания трудового образования и методика его обучения \(5A112101–Методика трудового обучения\)](#). Tashkent – 2014 g. s 107.

5. Zhuraev A.R. Research and methodology background to the optimization of labour and professional training curriculum in general secondary education // International scientific journal. № 7 (35) / Russia Volgograd. International scientific journal. № 7 (35) / «Science and world» – 0.325. 2016. – P. 70-71.

6. Zhuraev A.R. Using Electronic Teaching Materials for Training Future Teachers // “Eastern European Scientific Journal”. Auris Kommunikations – und Verlagsgesellschaft mbH. Journal ausgabe 1 – 2019. Germany. Pg, 432-435.

Electronic educational resources

1. www.ziyonet.uz

2. www.ziyonet.uz